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TOWARDS AN EMOTIONS-BASED ENGINEERING ETHICS EDUCATION

Roland Tormey

Teaching Support Centre (CAPE) & College of Humanities (CDH)
Ecole polytechnique fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL)
CH-1015, Lausanne, Switzerland

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ABSTRACT

Mainstream engineering ethics education focuses on the thinking processes that contribute to ethical decision making, rather than on the feeling processes. For example, major engineering ethics textbooks, tend to focus on different philosophical approaches to thinking through ethical dilemmas (Utilitarianism, Deontology etc.). Although emotionally-based alternative approaches (such as a feminist care ethics) are sometimes treated in passing they are not fundamental to the way in which the discipline is framed in these texts (which act as the major framework for many engineering ethics teachers). Although there has been some discussion in the wider literature about the relationship between emotions, risk, and ethics there has been a limited amount of empirical work in this vein.

Within the psychology and sociology of ethics, emotions are increasingly ascribed an important role, including a focus on 'moral emotions', and Haidt has argued that it is emotional responses, rather than rational processes, which often drive what is seen by the person as 'the right thing to do'. A sociological and psychological take on emotions also bring a range of other concepts into focus in thinking about engineering ethics, including notions of power, identity, responsibility, practices, and context. An emotions-based approach need not mean discounting ethical reasoning, but rather locating it in a whole-person context that includes thoughts, feelings, and the body.

This conceptual paper will explore what an emotions-based approach to engineering ethics means, and the implications of this for how engineering ethics are taught and learned.

1 INTRODUCTION

Mainstream engineering ethics education tends to focus on the *thinking processes* that contribute to ethical decision making, rather than on *emotional processes*. Looking, for example at major engineering textbooks, Van de Poel and Royakkers [1] define ethics as “the systemic reflection on what is moral”. They move on to describe ethics as being underpinned by three primary ethical theories (consequentialism, deontology and virtue ethics). While ‘care ethics’ is described in a short section, attempts to develop a care ethics in engineering is described as being “in its infancy” and notions of ‘care’ are rarely used in any significant way in the rest of the text. The word ‘emotion’ appears only 4 times in the whole book and is not related in any systematic way to ethics. The word empathy does not appear at all. Other mainstream textbooks also mention emotion and empathy at most in passing but do not treat them in any serious way.

This is surprising, given that emotions has grown to have an important role in academic discussions about moral action. In psychology and in sociology, the emotional revolution began in the 1980s and gained considerable ground in the 1990s. The growing academic interest in emotions was associated with a change in how emotions were understood in popular culture. While, throughout much of the history of western thought, emotions were understood principally as being a ‘threat to reason’ and as “much more primitive, less intelligent, more bestial, less dependable, and more dangerous than reason, and thus [needing] to be controlled by reason” [2], from the 1990s onwards emotions came to be framed in more positive ways, and in scientific and popular science literature became linked to ‘intelligence’ (Daniel Goldman), to rational decision making (António Damásio), and to success in social life and organisations (Frans de Waal). Part of this re-conceptualisation was the shifting of interest in moral psychology from a focus on moral reasoning to a focus on moral emotions [3,4].

This paper reviews recent literature on ‘emotions’ and ‘engineering ethics education’. It ends by highlighting some ideas as to how engineering ethics education can pivot towards a more emotionally-based (and perhaps more effective) approach.

2 METHODOLOGY

This paper is based on a review of literature in major engineering education journals (*Journal of Engineering Education* and *European Journal of Engineering Education* and *Science and Engineering Ethics*). Searches were carried out for articles which included references to “emotion*”, “empath*” and for articles which referenced (a) both “ethic*” AND “emotion*” or (b) both “ethic*” AND “empath*”.

This limited review was followed by a wider non-systematic, review of literature on ‘emotion’ and ‘engineering ethics’ and ‘education’.

3 EMOTION, ETHICS AND ENGINEERING EDUCATION

3.1 What is 'emotion' and which emotions are 'moral'?

Historically, emotions were conceived of as being in contradistinction to rationality. If lay theories of emotion have not moved far from this, contemporary empirical literature has moved beyond this separation such that emotions can be defined as a “complex, multicomponent episode that creates a readiness to act” [5].

Emotional episodes are typically understood as occurring in the context of a particular person-environment relationship. The environment in this case may be the physical environment but is often the social environment – emotions play a role in locating us with respect to others [7]. Within this context, the multiple components of an emotional episode include (i) cognitive appraisal of the person-environment relationship, (ii) a subjective appraisal of the situation which draws on both cultural resources and sense of identity, (iii) the disposition to think or act in particular ways, (iv) internal bodily changes (often linked to action dispositions), (v) facial expressions and (vi) responses to the emotion which may include acting on the environment, or on ourselves to regulate the emotion being experienced.

These components can be illustrated with a commonly recognised emotion such as anger: something happens in the social or physical environment which is cognitively appraised (i) as being unjust. This sense of injustice may be linked to social structures and hierarchies or to culture (ii). For example, an engineer may get angry if they are questioned closely about something within their area of expertise by a secretary, while the same questioning may not elicit anger if it came from a fellow engineer. Implicit in the emotion of anger is (iii) a disposition to act to ‘right the wrong’. This action is prepared for through bodily changes (iv) such as an increase in adrenaline and an increase in breath and heart rate. Alongside this, the person’s eyebrows are drawn down and together and their upper lip contracts (v). The person then responds in some way to this experience (vi), perhaps by re-thinking whether the secretary actually has expertise that the engineer had not anticipated, or by telling the secretary to stick to his or her own business. This response feeds back into and changes the ongoing emotion episode. The ‘emotion’ is not simply the bio-physical or subjective (‘feeling’) element of this process – emotion is the whole package which has to be understood simultaneously as social, cultural, bio-physical, and cognitive.

In this sense, emotions are not separate from cognition in the way in which they have typically been imagined in western thought. Cognitive appraisals (labelling a question as “insulting” or “insightful”) are intrinsic to how an emotion episode develops, while emotion regulation decisions are a result of emotional metacognition. Emotional bodily sensations also provide information to cognitive systems about our primary (pre-cognitive) appraisal of situations (e.g. one can have heightened awareness associated with fear before being consciously aware of what it is that one is frightened of, for example). This interlinking of ‘cognitive’ and ‘feeling’ is the origin of the idea of ‘emotional intelligence’, defined by the Yale team who coined the term

as the ability to perceive emotions in the self (congruence) and in others (empathy), to understand emotions (e.g. having a rich emotional vocabulary and identifying how emotions relate to each other, blend and change) and to use them to achieve goals, and to regulate emotions in the self and others [6] (since the term 'intelligence' is such a loaded one, these abilities are referred to here as 'emotional competences'). It is notable that empathy – framed here as a perspective-taking ability – is a core component of emotional competences, but emotional competences are framed here as wider than empathy.

Engineering ethics is commonly discussed in terms of social organisation with micro, meso, and macroethics issues corresponding to the micro, meso and macro levels of sociological study. If cognition is intrinsic to emotion, so too is social organisation. In the example above, the perceived social position of the questioner *vis a vis* the engineer contributes to development of anger. Jenkins and Oatley propose that emotions locate us in relation to other people across three dimensions depending on whether relationships give us a sense of Affiliation (warmth/affection), Attachment (safety/security), and Assertion (power or position within a social hierarchy) [7, p. 229]. Thus, feeling angry indicates a sense having a higher status or a sense of power with respect to another, while feeling shame indicates a sense of lower status or power (the Assertion dimension). On the Attachment dimension, feeling anxious or feeling trust indicates respectively a high or low distance from another, while on the Affiliation, feeling warmth towards or cold towards other people reflects a lesser or greater social distance.

At a superficial level it is easy to see that emotions give us a sense that something is 'good' or 'bad' and that they are therefore providing us with information which is profoundly connected to ethics. While there is a common sense focus on the valence of emotions (positive vs negative) it would be wrong to assume that negatively valenced emotions are morally unhelpful. Anger, for example, is described by Haidt [3, p. 856] as "perhaps the most underappreciated moral emotion", with moral emotions being defined as "those emotions that are linked to the interests or welfare either of society as a whole or at least of persons other than the judge or agent" [p.853]. Anger is one of a family of what Haidt describes as 'other condemning' moral emotions, along with contempt and disgust. Other important moral emotions include shame, embarrassment, guilt and pride (the self-conscious family), empathetic distress (other-suffering family), and gratitude and awe (other-praising family). It is worth noting that the term 'empathy' is used here again, but in a different sense (now an emotion rather than a cognitive competence). Empathetic distress at another's distress is identified as a crucially important moral emotion [8, 22], however the set of moral emotions is much wider than empathetic distress alone.

Viewed from an 'emotional competence' viewpoint, an emotion like anger is providing the person with information about an appraisal of injustice. However the component model of emotion highlights that anger does more than provide

information, it also generates thought-action tendencies and changed bodily states which may dispose a person towards more risky and careless decisions, something which may make it harder for people to engage in ethical reasoning processes [21]. Attending to emotional information is therefore, not enough. There is also a need to regulate emotion.

3.2 'Emotion' and 'Ethics' in Engineering Education literature

As was noted above, emotions are rarely substantively referenced in mainstream engineering ethics textbooks. In the engineering education research literature a focus on emotions has only begun to emerge in recent years.

In the last twenty years there has been some philosophical work on emotion in engineering ethics [for example 9, 10, 11] and, in line with the 'moral emotions' arguments developed in moral psychology, it has been claimed that "rather than being biases that threaten objectivity and rationality in thinking about acceptable risks, emotions contribute to a correct understanding of the moral acceptability of a hazard" [9, p.107]. This has led to arguments that engineers should be taught to accept the emotional dimensions of engineering, to use their discomfort to identify ethical issues, to think of their gut intuitions as a useful but unreliable sensor, and to practice linking 'reasonable' emotions to arguments [11]. It is worth noting that this framework follows the Yale model of emotional intelligence (as described above).

Among the first to look at what this might mean in practical terms in engineering ethics education is Theil et al. [12]. Noting that case studies are suitable for and widely used in engineering education, they argued that most cases are devoid of emotional content. They hypothesised that including information about the emotional responses of the case's primary character would facilitate retention and transfer of the case's knowledge content. Quantitative analysis of performance of 126 research participants indicated that recall of ethical cases was better when emotional content was included, as was performance on a transfer task. The focus here is on better learning of cognitive ethical content through emotional engagement, rather than on the development of emotional competences per se.

Sunderland [13] also provides a detailed account of integration of emotions-based ethical work into engineering education, this time through a PBL methodology. PBL's focus on complex and ill-bounded problems is identified as making it highly suitable for ethics education. In a 'story sharing' activity, students are asked to respond to 'technology in the news' stories emotively, as well as pre-reflectively, and reflectively. Emotional responses allow students to identify what is meaningful for them (and presumably to become aware of and find a language for their own emotional responses and those of others). Accounts of students learning are presented but described as preliminary. Furthermore while this work highlights the importance of 'emotion', there is little specific focus on particular emotions (guilt, pride, awe, joy, empathetic distress) or on a model of what emotional skills or knowledge were to be developed.

It was noted above that the concept of empathy is closely linked to that of emotion, and that empathetic distress is a fundamental moral emotion. More broadly, the concept of empathy has been used in engineering discourse over the last two decades. While this has often been in the context of ‘empathy work’ within the design process, empathy has also been linked to engineering ethics.

Walther and colleagues begin from a recognition that there is a “scarcity of conceptual models and empirical bases that limit the broader integration of empathy into the discussion and practices of engineering educators” [15, p.12; see also 16, p 535]. Inspired by exchanges with colleagues in Social Work education, Walther and colleagues seek to address these gaps by the development of a conceptual model of empathy as a learnable skill built on affective sharing, awareness of self and others, perspective taking, emotion regulation and the ability to metacognitively switch between analytical and empathetic modes. This is framed both within a professional practice orientation (which includes an understanding of micro, meso, and macrosocial systems) and a professional identity or ‘way of being’, which includes a focus on service to society [14]. This model moves beyond the more narrow definitions of empathy described above (and below) to treat empathy as a broad space in which to articulate a range of emotional competences. In later empirical work, they describe a facilitated experiential learning approach for developing empathy in engineering students and highlight how questions of social distance and of power/responsibility (questions which are encoded in emotional episodes) play out in students’ work in developing empathy skills. They also provide rich descriptions of students experiencing moral emotions such as pride, shame and distress at the distress of others [15]. While there is no systematic measurement of learning gains in comparison to a control group, rich and rigorously analysed qualitative accounts of learning from over 100 student participants are provided.

Hess and colleagues also focus on empathy and the related concept of care. The model of empathy which they use is more restricted than that of Walther and colleagues and frames empathy in terms a cognitive and emotional dimension and a self- and other-focused dimension [16]. They identify empathetic perspective-taking – a cognitive aspect of empathy – as a core skill, and note that at present there is little evidence about the processes that promote the empathic formation of students. Utilising the Scaffolded, Interactive, and Reflective Analysis (SIRA) framework [17], they describe integrating empathetic perspective-taking into a case study method to ethics teaching based on a Reflective Principalism approach. In their model, students first establish knowledge about the case, then engage in perspective taking before comparing and contrasting their perspective-taking work with other students. Thereafter they move on to decision-making followed by a meta-reflection. Qualitative interview-based data was collected from 19 participants. The interviews suggested that opportunities to share perspectives with others were important in the development of perspective-taking skills, including those which gave rise to a realisation that others viewed things in a different way – or indeed, in the same way but for different reasons. Although there is no control condition, participants did

claim a heightened ability to take perspectives and an ability to take perspectives of a wider range of stakeholders. In another study the same research team evaluated the impact of the SIRA approach using a number of quantitative measures of ethical reasoning as well as the Interpersonal Reactivity Index (IRI) to assess a number of dimensions of empathy [17]. Although participant numbers were not large (29 in test group) they did find statistically significant increases in empathetic perspective-taking and, based on a reduction in empathetic distress, they inferred that students also developed enhanced emotion regulation skills.

Gelfand [18] argues that moral psychology research has highlighted a number of features of ethical behaviour that are not typically addressed in 'moral reasoning' type courses. These include prior emotion or mood of the person, their available self-control resources, bystander effects, and dual systems thinking processes and associated routinized behaviours as well as primary (emotional) appraisals. As a result, he argues that existing ethics education approaches should be augmented by study of moral psychology and by the development of metacognitive abilities such that people can better regulate when and how to make ethical judgements. He describes doing this through using case studies of research findings presented alongside 'emotional coping' strategies. There is no data presented on the impact of this approach on student learning.

Steele and colleagues [19] and Higgs and colleagues [20] both worked within an Ethical Sensemaking approach which aims to include emotion within the ethical decision making process. For Steele, meta-cognitive emotion regulation was included as a strategy, along with a focus on situational and cognitive biases, in ethics training offered to students across a range of disciplines, including engineering. Using a pre-existing Ethical Decision Making measure (EDM) they evaluated the impact of their two-day research ethics training workshop on 127 participants and found significant increases in scores across a range of ethical strategies measures including 'dealing with emotions'. Higgs and colleagues [20] looked specifically at the experience of guilt, shame and embarrassment and its impact on moral decision making. Using an experimental design they used multiple versions of the same case study in order to generate the required emotions. They then looked at the impact of these emotions on participants' ethical decision making. They found that emotions of guilt and shame each changed the perceptions of the dilemma in question. Participants who felt shame, for example, reported highest levels of personal responsibility while those who felt guilt saw the problem as more pressing. They note, "contrary to common thought, experiencing no emotion while in an ethical dilemma may actually result in cognitive processes that could lead to less ethical decisions" [20, p.53]. Interestingly, they also found in their 1-hour long intervention that a structured approach to emotion regulation actually led to reduced use of metacognitive strategies and a reduction in sense of moral intensity. They suggest that this may be because the cognitive load induced by cognitive reappraisal may have hindered ethical sensemaking.

4 TOWARDS AN EMOTIONS-BASED ENGINEERING ETHICS

A review of the evidence on the role of emotions in engineering ethics education above suggests a number of directions that can be pursued in developing an effective, emotions-based approach.

First, much of the most interesting work in the field is emerging from interdisciplinary collaborations such as when engineering educators work with nursing educators, psychotherapists or social workers [e.g. 15]. These disciplines have a long history of work on developing emotional competence and empathy in students and their pedagogical approaches may well be adaptable to engineering situations.

Second, at a minimum, the introduction of emotional information into cases may have a positive impact on students retention and ability to apply what they have learned [12, 20]. However all emotions are not equal in this respect. There is some evidence in favour of a role for empathetic distress [22], guilt and shame [20] but not in favour of anger [21]. A greater focus on specific emotions may be more helpful than seeking to include 'emotions' in general.

Thirdly, most work proceeds on the basis that responding emotionally is not sufficient in itself, and that emotional information must contribute to an ethical reasoning process [e.g., 13,17]. This may mean, for example, emotively responding or perspective-taking early in the reasoning process followed by more 'cognitive' thinking strategies. However there is also evidence [20] that metacognitive emotion regulation strategies may also hinder effective ethical reasoning, at least if the total time available is short. Given the temporality of emotional episodes, spreading the ethical decision process over a longer period of time may be worth exploring.

Fourth, emotional competence skills (or 'empathy' as broadly defined by Walther and colleagues) may well help students to engage better in moral reasoning. However it is worth being clear as to what emotional competences are being targeted. The full range of emotional competences outlined, for example, in the Yale model [6], do not yet appear to have been integrated in any existing ethics intervention and the effects of learning to developing a range of emotional language, learning to recognise and name particular emotions in the self and others, learning about the effects of specific emotions on the body and on thought action tendencies, would be worth exploring.

Fifth, a range of pedagogies have been identified including (a) cases with emotional content, (b) including of 'perspective-taking' and 'perspective-comparing' stages during case analysis, (c) explicit teaching about cognitive and situational biases and emotion regulation strategies, and (d) experiential learning workshops focused on empathy skills. There is some initial evidence to support these strategies [12,17,19] but there are still far more questions than answers. Alongside the question of impact must be considered the question of measurement. There are a limited number of psychometric tools including emotional dimensions. Thus, development of appropriate assessment tools, and the use of rigorous qualitative methodologies, is a priority. This too will require interdisciplinary collaboration between engineering educators and those with expertise in social sciences.

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